

IMPROVING PERFORMANCES OF COMPLEMENTARY PAIR LMS ALGORITHM

Radu Ciprian Bilcu¹, Pauli Kuosmanen² and Corneliu Rusu³

Signal Processing Laboratory, Digital Media Institute, Tampere University of Technology,
P.O.BOX 553, FIN-33101, Tampere, FINLAND

e-mail: ¹bilcu@cs.tut.fi, ²pqo@cs.tut.fi, ³cornelin@cs.tut.fi

ABSTRACT

In this paper we discuss how to improve the behavior of the CP-LMS algorithm that was proposed by Min-Soo Park and Woo-Jin Song [5]. The difference between the new algorithm and CP-LMS algorithm is that the new algorithm uses two LMS algorithms that operate in parallel, one with large and fixed step and another with variable step. The coefficients of the novel variable step algorithm are re-initialized by the coefficients of the algorithm with fixed step whenever possible. In the meantime the step-size of the proposed algorithm is increased or decreased if the algorithm is respectively far or near to the optimum.

1 INTRODUCTION

In adaptive filtering the LMS (Least Mean Square) algorithm is very popular because of its simplicity. It is known that for the LMS algorithm if we need a fast convergence speed we must use an relatively large step-size, but this step-size will produce a large steady-state error. To obtain a small steady-state error a small step-size is used, but this step-size will produce a small convergence speed for the LMS algorithm [1].

In this paper we propose a new algorithm that can provide a fast convergence speed and a small steady-state error. The new algorithm named Complementary Pair Variable Step LMS algorithm (CPVSLMS algorithm) is a CP-LMS type algorithm [5] but its step is in a different manner adjusted in order to provide a faster convergence speed than the CP-LMS algorithm.

2 THE CP-LMS ALGORITHM

The CP-LMS algorithm proposed by Min-Soo Park and Woo-Jin Song in [5], consists of two LMS algorithm that operate in parallel. The block diagram of this algorithm is presented in Fig.(1).

The accuracy mode filter is an LMS filter with small step-size μ_1 and the speed mode filter is an LMS filter with large step-size μ_2 . The controller re-initializes the coefficients of the accuracy filter with the coefficients of the speed filter for every T -th iterations when the local average of the squared error of the accuracy filter

Figure 1: The block diagram of the CP-LMS algorithm for system identification

is greater than the local average of the squared error of the speed filter for L consecutive comparisons of last T samples.

The coefficients of the speed filter are updated by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n+1) = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n) + \mu_2 e_2(n) \mathbf{x}(n). \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n)$, $\mathbf{x}(n)$ are the vector of the filter coefficients and the vector of the input, respectively, $e_2(n)$ is the error of the adaptive filter

$$e_2(n) = y(n) + w(n) - y_2(n), \quad (2)$$

and $w(n)$ is the output noise.

The coefficients of the accuracy filter are updated by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n+1) = \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n+1), & \text{if } n \bmod T = 0 \text{ and} \\ & \prod_{i=1}^L Q(n-iT) = 1; \\ \hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n) + 2\mu_1 e_1(n) \mathbf{x}(n), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where T is the length of the comparison interval, L is the number of comparisons and $Q(m)$ is defined as:

$$Q(m) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \sum_{i=m}^{m+T} e_1^2(i) > \sum_{i=m}^{m+T} e_2^2(i); \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

3 THE CPVSLMS ALGORITHM

The new algorithm uses the idea of the CP-LMS algorithm that was proposed in [5] but the difference between the two algorithms consists in that the step-size μ_1 will be variable in the case of the new algorithm. For the beginning the value of the step $\mu_1(0)$ will be $\mu_3 < \mu_2$.

In the case of the CPVSLMS algorithm the coefficients of the filter with step $\mu_1(n)$ will be re-initialized in the same way as in the CP-LMS algorithm when the local average of the $e_1^2(n)$ is greater than the local average of the $e_2^2(n)$. In the same time the step $\mu_1(n+1)$ will be re-initialized with the value $\frac{\mu_2 + \mu_1(n)}{2}$ when the coefficients are re-initialized. Thus to increase the convergence speed in the case of the new algorithm the step-size is increased. When the filter with step $\mu_1(n)$ goes faster to the convergence than the speed filter, the step $\mu_1(n)$ will be decreased in order to obtain a small steady-state error. Therefore the behavior of the CPVSLMS algorithm can be mathematically expressed as:

1. The update of the coefficients of the speed filter:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n+1) = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n) + \mu_2 e_2(n) \mathbf{x}(n), \quad (5)$$

where

$$e_2(n) = y(n) + w(n) - y_2(n). \quad (6)$$

2. The update of the coefficients of the variable step filter:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n+1) = \begin{cases} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n+1), & \text{if } n \bmod T = 0 \text{ and} \\ & \prod_{i=1}^L Q(n-iT) = 1; \\ \hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n) + 2\mu_1(n)e_1(n)\mathbf{x}(n), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

3. The re-initialization of the variable step:

$$\mu_1(n+1) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu_2 + \mu_1(n)}{2}, & \text{if } n \bmod T = 0 \text{ and} \\ & \prod_{i=1}^L Q(n-iT) = 1; \\ \max\{\alpha\mu_1(n), \mu_3\}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$Q(m) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \sum_{i=m}^{m+T} e_1^2(i) > \sum_{i=m}^{m+T} e_2^2(i); \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

As we can see from the above equations the basic idea of this algorithm is to increase the step-size when the algorithm converges slowly than the algorithm with large and fixed step-size and decrease the step-size when algorithm is near the steady-state. The minimum value of the step $\mu_1(n)$ is obtained when the algorithm is on the steady-state and will be μ_3 . The maximum value of the $\mu_1(n)$ is obtained when the algorithm is far from the steady-state and can be in some cases very closed to μ_2 , but always will be smaller than μ_2 .

For the value of μ_2 and μ_3 we can choose any value as long as the convergence is obtained. But if the value of μ_2 is close to the value of μ_3 then when the step $\mu_1(n)$ is decreasing from his maximum value to μ_3 , we will have an small number of re-initialization of $\mu_1(n)$. Therefore in order to provide a large number of modifications of step $\mu_1(n)$ we must chose $\mu_3 \ll \mu_2$. Therefore the values of this parameters will be chosen as [1]:

$$\mu_3 \ll \mu_2 < \frac{1}{N \epsilon \{x^2(n)\}}, \quad (10)$$

where notation: $\epsilon \{ \}$ denote the expectation. The lower bound of the step-sizes can be chosen in such a way to achieve convergence within the given training signal length K .

The value of the parameter α in equation (8) must be in the interval $(0, 1)$, so that the step $\mu_1(n)$ will be decreased when the algorithm goes to the steady-state. If the value of α is close to 0, then the value of $\mu_1(n)$ is decreased too fast. If the value of α is close to 1, then the algorithm will have too small convergence speed. In our simulations we use $\alpha = 0.6$.

The parameters T and L can be chosen in the same way as for the CP-LMS algorithm. Therefore for the value of T we choose $\sqrt{K}$, where K is the length of the training input sequence. For the parameter L , we choose the value $L = 3$ [5] that shows good behavior in simulations.

The number of computations that are needed for the CPVSLMS algorithm at each test interval of length T are: $2T + 2N + 7$ multiplications and $2T + 4N + 1$ additions.

3.1 The Algorithm Behavior

To examine the behavior of the CPVSLMS algorithm we will use the estimation error vectors:

$$\mathbf{p}_1(n) = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n) - \mathbf{h}; \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{p}_2(n) = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n) - \mathbf{h}, \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n)$ is the coefficients vector of the filter with variable step, $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_2(n)$ is the coefficients vector of the speed filter and $\mathbf{h}$ is the coefficients vector of the unknown system.

In order to simplify the analysis we will make some assumptions. First we will assume that the training sequence and the estimates coefficients are uncorrelated,

and the input sequence $\mathbf{x}(n)$ is white Gaussian signal so that the autocorrelation matrix is of the form $\mathbf{R} = \sigma_x^2 \mathbf{I}$. If we observe that the value of the step $\mu_1(n)$ is changed only once on the interval of length T then the value of the step $\mu_1(n)$ is constant inside of this interval so the second assumption is that inside of the interval of length T we can consider that the expectation $\epsilon \{\mu_1(n)\} = \mu_1(n)$.

Combining (5), (6) and (12) the recursive equation of $\mathbf{p}_2(n)$ is:

$$\mathbf{p}_2(n+1) = (I - \mu_2 \mathbf{x}^T(n) \mathbf{x}(n)) \mathbf{p}_2(n) + \mu_2 w(n) \mathbf{x}(n), \quad (13)$$

Thus, the mean behavior of $\mathbf{p}_1(n)$ and $\mathbf{p}_2(n)$ will be described by [5] :

$$\epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_2(n+1)\} = (I - \mu_2 \mathbf{R}) \epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_2(n)\}; \quad (14)$$

$$\epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_1(n+1)\} = \begin{cases} \epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_2(n+1)\}, & \text{if } n \bmod T = 0 \text{ and} \\ & \prod_{i=1}^L Q(n-iT) = 1; \\ (I - \mu_1(n) \mathbf{R}) \epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_1(n)\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The mean square behavior of the two filters are estimated by [5] :

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_2^T(n+1) \mathbf{p}_2(n+1)\} &= \epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_2(n+1)\|^2 \right\} \\ &= \beta_2 \epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_2(n)\|^2 \right\} + N \mu_2^2 \sigma_x^2 \sigma_w^2 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\sigma_w^2 = \epsilon \{w^2(n)\}$ and $\beta_2 = 1 - 2\mu_2 \sigma_x^2 + (N+2)\mu_2^2 \sigma_x^4$.

The mean-square behavior of $\mathbf{p}_1(n)$ is described by [5]:

$$\epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_1^T(n+1) \mathbf{p}_1(n+1)\} = \epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_1(n+1)\|^2 \right\}, \quad (17)$$

$$\epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_1(n+1)\|^2 \right\} = \begin{cases} \epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_2(n+1)\|^2 \right\}, & \text{if} \\ & n \bmod T = 0 \\ \text{and } \prod_{i=1}^L Q(n-iT) = 1; \\ \beta_1 \epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_1(n)\|^2 \right\} + N \mu_1^2(n) \sigma_x^2 \sigma_w^2, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where $\beta_1 = 1 - 2\mu_1(n) \sigma_x^2 + (N+2)\mu_1^2(n) \sigma_x^4$.

From the equations (14), (15), (16) and (18) we can obtain the steady-state properties of the CPVSLMS algorithm:

$$\epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_2(\infty)\} = 0; \quad (19)$$

$$\epsilon \{\mathbf{p}_1(\infty)\} = 0; \quad (20)$$

$$\epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_2(\infty)\|^2 \right\} = \frac{N \mu_2 \sigma_w^2}{2 - (N+2)\mu_2 \sigma_x^2}; \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_1(\infty)\|^2 \right\} &= \frac{N \mu_1(\infty) \sigma_w^2}{2 - (N+2)\mu_1(\infty) \sigma_x^2} = \\ &= \frac{N \mu_3 \sigma_w^2}{2 - (N+2)\mu_3 \sigma_x^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

4 SIMULATIONS RESULTS

The performance of the CPVSLMS algorithm is measured with the norm squared error:

$$\left\| \hat{\mathbf{b}}_1(n) \right\|^2 = \left\| \hat{\mathbf{h}}_1(n) - \mathbf{h} \right\|^2.$$

The algorithms which are compared with the CPVSLMS algorithm are: the LMS algorithm with large step $\mu = 0.04$, the LMS algorithm with small step $\mu = 0.0004$, and the CP-LMS algorithm with parameters $\mu_2 = 0.04$, $\mu_1 = 0.0004$, $T = 100$ and $L = 3$. The parameters of the CPVSLMS algorithm are: $\mu_2 = 0.04$, $\mu_3 = 0.0004$, $T = 100$, $\alpha = 0.6$ and $L = 3$.

In Fig.(2) the output noise is assumed to be white Gaussian pseudo-random with $\epsilon \{w(n)\} = 0$, $\epsilon \{w^2(n)\} = 0.001$.

In Fig.(3) the output noise is assumed to be uniform distributed with $\epsilon \{w(n)\} = 0$, $\epsilon \{w^2(n)\} = 0.001$.

In Fig.(4) the output noise is assumed to be white Gaussian pseudo-random with $\epsilon \{w(n)\} = 0$, $\epsilon \{w^2(n)\} = 0.01$.

The input signal is white Gaussian pseudo-random with $\epsilon \{x(n)\} = 0$ and $\epsilon \{x^2(n)\} = 1$.

Fig.(2), Fig.(3) and Fig.(4) show the simulations in non-stationary environments when the model of the unknown system is $H_1(z)$ for the first 5000 iterations and $H_2(z)$ for the last 5000 iterations:

$$\begin{aligned} H_1(z) &= 0.5082(1 + 0.9z^{-1} + 0.8z^{-2} + 0.7z^{-3} \\ &\quad + 0.6z^{-4} + 0.5z^{-5} + 0.4z^{-6} + 0.3z^{-7} + 0.2z^{-8} \\ &\quad + 0.1z^{-9}); \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} H_2(z) &= 0.5082(-1 + 0.9z^{-1} - 0.8z^{-2} + 0.7z^{-3} \\ &\quad - 0.6z^{-4} + 0.5z^{-5} - 0.4z^{-6} + 0.3z^{-7} - 0.2z^{-8} \\ &\quad + 0.1z^{-9}). \end{aligned}$$

The scale factor 0.5082 in $H_1(z)$ and $H_2(z)$ makes the input power and the output power equal for the two models so that $SNR = +30$ dB in Fig.(2) and Fig.(3) and $SNR = +20$ dB in Fig.(4).

By LMS1 we denote the LMS algorithm with step-size $\mu = 0.0004$, LMS2 denotes the LMS algorithm with step-size $\mu = 0.04$ and CP-LMS denote the CP-LMS algorithm with $\mu_1 = 0.0004$, $\mu_2 = 0.04$, $T = 100$ and $L = 3$. CPVSLMS denotes the new algorithm with the parameters: $\mu_2 = 0.04$, $\mu_3 = 0.0004$, $T = 100$, $L = 3$ and $\alpha = 0.6$.

In simulation presented in Fig. (2) we have used the parameters $\mu_3 = 0.0004$, $\sigma_x^2 = 1$, $\sigma_w^2 = 0.001$, $N = 10$. With these values we obtain in equation (22)

Figure 2: Comparisons of LMS1, LMS2, CP-LMS and CPVSLMS for gaussian distributed noise $SNR = +30$ dB

$\epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_1(\infty)\|^2 \right\}_{dB} = -56.98$ dB. This value is obtained also from the simulation (see Fig. (2)).

For the simulation in Fig. (4) we have used the parameters $\mu_3 = 0.0004$, $\sigma_x^2 = 1$, $\sigma_w^2 = 0.01$, $N = 10$, and in this case we obtain in equation (22) $\epsilon \left\{ \|\mathbf{p}_1(\infty)\|^2 \right\}_{dB} = -46.98$ dB. And also in this case the simulation prove the theoretical considerations (see Fig. (4)).

5 CONCLUSIONS

By using a variable step-size for the CP-LMS algorithm, we introduce a new algorithm that can provide a faster convergence speed than the CP-LMS algorithm when the steady-state errors of both the CP-LMS and CPVSLMS algorithms are equal. Also we demonstrate that the theoretical results are proved by the simulations.

Although the CPVSLMS algorithm requires more computations than the CP-LMS and than the single fixed step-size algorithm, the performance of the algorithm outweigh the extra cost.

References

- [1] S. S. Haykin, *Adaptive Filter Theory*, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1991.
- [2] Glen Zelniker, Fred J. Taylor, *Advanced Digital Signal processing - Theory and applications*, Marcel Dekker Inc., 1993.
- [3] R. H. Kwong and E. W. Johnston, *A variable step size LMS algorithm*, IEEE Trans. on Signal Processing, vol 40, no.7, pp.1633-1642, Jul. 1992.
- [4] D. W. Kim, J. H. Choi, Y. S. Choi, C. H. Jeon and H. Y. Ko, *A VS-LMS Algorithm Using Normalized*

Figure 3: Comparisons of LMS1, LMS2, CP-LMS and CPVSLMS for uniform distributed noise $SNR = +30$ dB

Absolute Estimation Error, IEEE TENCON-Digital Signal Processing Applications, 1996.

- [5] Min-Soo Park and Woo-Jin Song, *A Complementary Pair LMS Algorithm for Adaptive Filtering*, IEICE Trans. Fundamentals, vol. E81-A, no. 7, pp. 1493-1496, July, 1998.

Figure 4: Comparisons of LMS1, LMS2, CP-LMS, and CPVSLMS for gaussian distributed noise $SNR = +20$ dB